

Deliverable D1.2 Data Management Plan

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Australian Imaging Services
BIA	BioImage Archive
CSA	Coordination and Support Actions
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMPIAR	Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive
ERIC	Euro-BioImaging European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EWP	EURO-BIOIMAGING Web Portal
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GBI	Global BioImaging
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIDE	Global Image Data Ecosystem
IDR	Image Data Resource
LLM	Large Language Models
ML	Machine Learning
NIF	Australian National Imaging Facility
OME	Open Microscopy Environment
RDF	Resource Description Format

SSBD	Systems Science of Biological Dynamics
XNAT	Extensible Neuroimaging Archive Toolkit

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable comprises the initial iteration of the foundingGIDE Data Management Plan, detailing the procedures for managing various data types generated throughout project activities. It delineates the collection, processing, and generation of data, as well as the sharing, openness, and preservation strategies. This document will act as a guide for all foundingGIDE consortium partners, aiding in the implementation of specified measures and activities to attain project goals. Updates to this deliverable will be made as necessary to accommodate adaptations and changes during project advancement.

Overall, the primary focus of the project is on improving global capacity for management of imaging data through shared standards and outreach. As such, the project activities generate very little data directly, this generation is primarily through WP10, which will create aggregated metadata from existing repositories.

1. Project Description

The exponential growth of digital image data in biological research, driven by advancing imaging technologies, has led to challenges in sharing this data openly. Efforts to address these challenges, such as developing file formats and metadata standards, often remain regional. This project aims to establish a Global Image Data Ecosystem (GIDE) connecting biological and biomedical image data resources worldwide. European, Australian, and Japanese stakeholders will collaborate to develop standards for data and metadata sharing, serving as a blueprint for global engagement. Harmonised ontologies and metadata models will facilitate communication between diverse resources. Proof of concept implementations will demonstrate the feasibility of these standards, fostering global adoption. GIDE will democratise bioimage data, fostering innovative research globally.

This Data Management Plan (DMP) is formulated in accordance with the Guidelines on FAIR data management in Horizon Europe and EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR). The DMP has also been formulated in recognition of the need for compatibility with privacy provisions in international jurisdictions, specifically Japan and Australia. This first version of the Data Management Plan has been prepared according to the Horizon Europe DMP template. The document describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the project. The plan is developed to ensure that the research data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR). The DMP is not fixed but is rather a living document that will evolve during the duration of the project and will be updated in the future as needed.

The foundingGIDE project is a coordination and support actions (CSA) type Horizon Europe project where the primary objectives are to strengthen existing imaging infrastructure networks within European institutes and to develop partnerships with Australian and Japanese counterparts. These activities will leverage existing networks of the Euro-BioImaging European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Australian Imaging Services (AIS), Microscopy Australia, Australian National Imaging Facility (NIF), Japanese Systems Science of Biological Dynamics (SSBD), Open Microscopy Environment (OME) and Global BioImaging (GBI). Together the community will survey the landscape of existing metadata standards and ontologies and develop recommendations to support standardisation of data across repositories. The project will engage with the community using networking activities, disseminate its learnings by communicating to the community and, facilitate policy development and mutual learning. It will coordinate with the imaging infrastructures to create the networks and develop working strategies. Landscape analysis of biological and preclinical imaging ontologies will be performed across the continents engaging experts from the community to develop recommendations which could be applied to specific data resources at partner sites. Efforts will be made to have select ontologies be sustainable and have centralised coordination which will promote consistency between biological and preclinical imaging practices. The project will also provide recommendations on core metadata elements which should be included to have compatibility and discoverability across resources. This core set of metadata items will set the stage for the project's long term strategy and help others data resources align with the foundingGIDE ecosystem. The project will also practically apply the developed metadata models to the existing imaging databases BioImage Archive (BIA), Image Data Resource (IDR), Systems Science of Biological Dynamics (SSBD), Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (EMPIAR) and Extensible Neuroimaging Archive Toolkit (XNAT), thereby enabling findability in the EURO-BIOIMAGING Web Portal (EWP). Through its efforts the project seeks to have a common language and framework for imaging data making it compatible and shareable across different repositories thereby elevating the FAIR principles.

2. Data Summary

The foundingGIDE project will adopt common ontologies and harmonise metadata among data resources with close collaboration with research infrastructure users and node staff. The entire foundation of the project is developed with Open Science in mind where all outcomes of the project are open and available to researchers and the general public. Having said that, there will be no new research data generated during the project. Data mentioned here always refers to metadata (associated data for data). Any software tools that will be developed will be available under open licence.

Due to the nature of the project, many coordination events will be organised. From these event registrations, contacts will be gathered and stored for communication regarding the events and possibly in the future for successfully enabling a foundingGIDE ecosystem. All contacts will be stored and handled confidentially and in compliance with GDPR. Appropriate disclaimers will be provided at the point of collection. The contact information will be stored during the duration of the project and will be deleted after the project's obliged retention period.

Project partners will be involved in developing training materials on the use of ontologies and metadata. The educational material will be made openly available through widely used existing resources like the Global BioImaging training resource.

Reuse of Existing Data

The metadata from the three existing repositories (BIA, IDR, SSBD) will form the basis of the data deliverable. This data is essential for creating a unified, searchable metadata snapshot across globally distinct bioimaging data resources. The metadata from these repositories is assumed to be available under the CC0 licence, though it may be under different licences. reuse of existing data was considered crucial as it enables the demonstration of a practical combination of metadata from disparate systems, laying the groundwork for more frequent and efficient metadata exchange between these systems. Discarding the reuse of this data was not considered, as it is integral to achieving the project's objectives of simplifying search and discovery, and making bioimaging data more accessible.

Types and Formats of Data

The exported and harmonised metadata will be represented as an Resource Description Format (RDF). This format facilitates the integration and querying of metadata across different systems, adhering to the FAIR principles. RDF graphs are particularly suitable for representing linked data and ensuring interoperability between different bioimaging data resources.

Purpose of Data Generation or reuse

The purpose of data generation or reuse is to simplify search and discovery and make the data more accessible. By creating a harmonised, linked metadata snapshot, the project aims to enable shared search across globally distinct bioimaging data resources. This aligns with the project's objectives to demonstrate a concrete combination of metadata from disparate systems and to develop a search prototype that leverages the identified minimal metadata sets.

Expected Size of Data

The exported metadata will be in the 100GB - 1TB range uncompressed. This estimate accounts for the comprehensive nature of the metadata being extracted and harmonised from the participating repositories. The size reflects the extensive and detailed metadata required to enable effective search and discovery across multiple bioimaging datasets.

Origin/Provenance of the Data

The data will originate from the three existing repositories (BIA, IDR, SSBD). These repositories contain rich, diverse bioimaging metadata that, when combined, will provide a comprehensive snapshot of available bioimaging data. The provenance of this data ensures that it is reliable and relevant for the project's objectives.

Data Utility Outside the Project

The data might be useful to individuals or organisations attempting to find publicly available image data for reuse or those trying to identify gaps in existing experiments. Researchers, data scientists, and bioimaging professionals could benefit from this harmonised metadata to discover available datasets, plan new experiments, and ensure efficient use of existing data. The data utility extends beyond the immediate project, supporting broader scientific discovery and innovation in the field of bioimaging.

3. FAIR data

The project enables coordination of repositories which host the largest collection of openly accessible, biological datasets currently available and boasts to being the gold standard for data sharing. Through its coordination efforts the project aims to bridge the gap between the resources and develop common choice of ontologies, metadata models and sharing of mapped metadata. This will elevate the standards of FAIR research data management globally. The developments made will be recorded, maintained and popularised via FAIRsharing (<https://fairsharing.org/>) interoperability resource.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The project partners will agree on a common data catalogue which will make image data easily discoverable by generic services like openAIRE¹. The test portal developed in WP11 will enable searching for imaging datasets across the three primary repositories engaged in this project, SSBD, IDR and BIA.

Use of persistent identifiers

Internally to the metadata graph, the persistent identifiers from the original resources will be used. This ensures that data reusers are aware that these identifiers are not newly created but represent further expressions of existing metadata. These persistent identifiers will facilitate navigation back to the original data, maintaining a clear link to the source repositories.

¹ <http://www.openaire.eu/>

Use of Metadata

Only rich metadata will be provided within the scope of this project. While the original data will remain in the three source repositories (BIA, IDR, SSBD), the metadata will encompass detailed provenance information such as author, licence, and more. For each repository, a detailed and partially overlapping list of richer metadata will be created. This list will include information specific to each repository, such as IDR will provide metadata which will include biomolecular information, phenotypic information, and other relevant details for each image.

The metadata will follow disciplinary standards as defined by several work packages (e.g., WP2 for chosen ontologies and WP7 for minimal metadata sets). These standards ensure the metadata is comprehensive and aligns with the FAIR principles.

Search keywords included in metadata

Unique terms based on the ontologies chosen by other work packages will be prime candidates for search keywords. These terms will enhance the searchability and discoverability of the metadata. However, the project aims to go beyond merely providing search keywords by creating a robust, interoperable metadata framework that allows for advanced search and discovery functionalities.

The metadata will be structured into RDF graphs which is a W3C standard. This structure allows the metadata to be easily harvested and indexed by various data repositories and search engines. RDF graphs facilitate the integration and querying of metadata, ensuring it is accessible and interoperable across different bioimaging data resources.

3.2. Making data accessible

Repository

Data will be deposited in a trusted repository. A compressed version of the metadata will be deposited in Zenodo². If the compressed artefact is under 50GB, it will be stored in a single Zenodo entry. If it exceeds this size, steps will be taken to address Zenodo's size limit, potentially through splitting the data or using multiple entries. Additional representations, such as hosting on GitHub, may also be considered to increase accessibility.

Zenodo assigns DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) to the deposited data, ensuring persistent identification and resolution to a digital object. The digital object will be a compressed version of the metadata, which, while not ideal for direct manipulation, will still provide accessible and interoperable data.

Data

The metadata set will be made openly available. The original metadata that is being exported and harmonised is already openly available, ensuring compliance with open data principles. If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/gide/>

The metadata will be accessible via HTTP for download and represented in RDF for parsing. Additionally, there may be a provision for adding a SPARQL endpoint, enabling live querying of the metadata without needing to download it.

Metadata

All the metadata will be made openly available and licensed under CC0. The metadata will contain sufficient information to enable users to access the underlying data. The compressed metadata archive will remain available as long as CERN continues to support Zenodo, providing a high level of long-term preservation. Other representations, such as those on GitHub, may be taken offline after the project concludes due to the size of the uncompressed data.

The data format (RDF) is a widely used standard, there is extensive software already available for handling it. Documentation on how to best utilise these tools will be included to facilitate data access and manipulation.

3.3. Making data interoperable

The lack of interoperability among different imaging data resources is one of the primary drivers of the foundingGIDE project. The project aims to reduce the lack of common standards for storing data and metadata by engaging the community and creating converging global standards for metadata. These efforts are going to have a direct impact on enabling data interoperability across data repositories and scientific categories.

We will adhere to the guidelines defined within the work packages (WPs) since there are no community-endorsed best practices. Specifically, we will use the ontologies chosen in WP2 and the minimal metadata sets identified in WP7. These standards and methodologies will ensure our data is interoperable, facilitating data exchange and reuse across various bioimaging disciplines.

If we need to use uncommon or project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, we will provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies. We will also openly publish any generated ontologies or vocabularies to enable reuse, refinement, or extension by the broader community. This approach ensures that even project-specific developments contribute to the wider field and remain accessible for future research.

The project will include qualified references to other data. The Linked Data³ representation of the metadata in the existing three repositories (BIA, IDR, SSBD) is a core objective. This linkage will enable users to navigate between related datasets and integrate information from different sources seamlessly.

3.4. Increase data reuse

The adoption of common metadata standards across research infrastructures allows data to be searched using codified terms making it discoverable. The discovery of data will facilitate data sharing and reuse. Bringing the imaging community together will promote harmonisation of data handling procedures which will expand the opportunities by promoting data access to multiple research infrastructures. The strict use of metadata standards along with appropriate ontologies are intended to promote training of artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML) and large language

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Linked_data

models (LLM) which in turn provide their learnings through trained models. The accuracy of these models is dependent on the availability of curated datasets with rich metadata. The project gathers recommendations for having core metadata parameters which are essential for describing data.

To validate data analysis and facilitate data reuse, we will provide comprehensive documentation. This will include readme files detailing methodology, codebooks, data cleaning procedures, analyses, variable definitions, and units of measurement. Additionally, we will demonstrate how to process the harmonised metadata and provide links to Jupyter notebooks or host it on GitHub. These notebooks will serve as practical examples, making it easier for users to understand and reuse the data effectively.

The data is already freely available in the original repositories. The harmonised metadata will also be made freely available and licensed using standard reuse licences, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement. This ensures maximum accessibility and reuse potential. The data will be usable by third parties, particularly after the end of the project. The RDF format ensures long-term usability and parseability, and the repository (Zenodo) is highly reliable. The ontologies used will be supported by institutions like EMBL-EBI, ensuring continued relevance and support.

The provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards. The specific standards will be chosen based on community consensus during the project, ensuring comprehensive and consistent provenance information.

During the harmonisation of the ontologies, we will generate reports detailing all the used ontology terms to identify outliers, typos, and other data-cleaning issues. This process will ensure the accuracy and consistency of the harmonised metadata, maintaining high data quality.

4. Other research outputs

The foundingGIDE project will develop tools for image data search and recording metadata. These will be openly available to users along with supporting documentation. For digital outputs, such as software, workflows, protocols, and models, we will use GitHub repositories to manage and share these resources. Each repository will be assigned a Zenodo DOI to ensure persistent identification and facilitate citation. This approach aligns with best practices for making digital research outputs FAIR. All digital outputs will be registered with unique DOIs through Zenodo and indexed in relevant databases such as MicroscopyDB. Outputs will be publicly accessible via GitHub and Zenodo, ensuring that users can download and use the resources without restrictions. We will use standard formats and protocols to ensure interoperability. Comprehensive documentation, including readme files, user manuals, and training materials, will be provided to facilitate reuse. We will also provide example workflows and protocols to help users integrate our outputs into their own research.

Additionally, any new software or tools developed will be open-sourced under appropriate licences, allowing others to modify and extend them. We will also ensure that any protocols, models, and workflows adhere to community standards and are validated with example data sets to demonstrate their applicability and reliability. By following these practices, we aim to maximise the impact and utility of all research outputs generated during the project, ensuring they are as useful and accessible to the broader scientific community as the data itself.

5. Allocation of resources

The primary focus of this proposal is to make the datasets FAIR. The estimated time and effort for harmonising the metadata include significant contributions from all participants. This includes model gap analysis, defining necessary mappings, extracting and validating metadata, and publishing the harmonised metadata. The detailed effort and costs are outlined in the project proposal.

Minimal storage costs are expected as public repositories like Zenodo will be used. Additional storage required for intermediate steps will be provided by the participants at their own locations for the duration of the grant. Data will be managed within secure, trusted repositories with robust security protocols. Costs related to making the data FAIR, including storage and harmonisation efforts, are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

Data management oversight will be provided through the coordination efforts of WP1. The DMP will detail all matters related to data and will be updated when necessary. Specific tasks within WP10 will be managed by GerBI-OME, EMBL-EBI, and RIKEN as outlined in the project description.

Long-term preservation of project output will be ensured through the use of Zenodo, which supports long-term data preservation policies. According to Zenodo's policies⁴, data will be preserved for a minimum of 20 years. Costs for long-term preservation are minimal and covered under the existing infrastructure of Zenodo. The value lies in ensuring continued access to harmonised metadata for future research. The decision to use Zenodo for long-term preservation was made collectively by the project participants based on Zenodo's reliability and commitment to data preservation.

6. Data security

The data will be safely stored in trusted repositories like Zenodo, which ensures long-term preservation and curation through its robust infrastructure and commitment to data security. Zenodo ensures data security through robust measures including encrypted data storage and transmission, stringent access controls, regular secure backups, and compliance with international standards. The repository employs secure user authentication, continuous monitoring, and regular security audits to maintain data integrity and prevent unauthorised access. These comprehensive protocols ensure the protection and reliability of data stored in Zenodo.

7. Ethics

The outcomes of the foundingGIDE project are intended for researchers, research infrastructures and the general public irrespective of gender, background, or geographical location. FoundingGIDE activities will be conducted according to national legal and ethical requirements of the EU, Japan and Australia. It will comply with Horizon Europe ethical standards and guidelines and with the provisions of the GDPR for the collection and processing of personal data in meetings, communication and dissemination activities.

⁴ <https://help.zenodo.org/guides/nih/element4/>

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